

Attended event	Event type	Organizer	Host	Partner who attended	Location of the event	Date	Size of the audience (<10, 10-20, 20-50, 50-100, 100-200, >200)	Type of audience (SMEs and Industry, Data owners, Data providers, Academic community, Open Source community, etc.)	Mean of promoting the project (dissemination material, face-to-face discussion, etc.)	Link to the event's website (if available)	Number of persons reached	Description of the activity
BDV PPP Summit				ATOS	Porto, Portugal		>400	all	diss material	https://www.big-data-value.eu/bdvppp-summit-2020/		
EBDFV 2020				ATOS	Berlin, Germany		> 600	all	diss material	https://www.european-big-data-value-forum.eu/		
BDV PPP GOING VIRTUAL – DATA PLATFORM WEBINARS Big Data PPP Mixed Data Platforms: "B2B and B2C together"	Webinar	BDVA, the BDVe project and the EC	BDVA, BDVe, EC	ATB	online	06.05.2020	ca.200	all	online presentation	https://www.big-data-value.eu/bdv-ppp-going-virtual-data-platform-webinars/	approx. 200	This webinar was organised by the BDVA, the BDVe project and the EC as a first event in a of events and workshops related to the EU big data platform projects that are funded under the umbrella of the European Big Data Value PPP
Using the Connected Car's Digital Data in the Real World	Webinar	SBD Automotive and LexisNexis Risk Solutions	SBD Automotive and LexisNexis Risk Solutions	ATB, LNRS	online	24.09.2020	>160	all	online presentation	https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=Hzim8t8MHXM	approx. 160	
NODES 2020 Neo4j Online Developer Expo and Summit	online conference	Neo4j	Neo4j	UIBK	online	20/10/2020	>600	all	online presentation	https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=oiPiWzjz9U		Presenting how knowledge graphs can be used as a solution for consent representation, visualization and management.
SEMIC Conference 2020	online conference	EU	EU, Germany	LUH, UBO	online	15/10/2020	>200	all	online discussion	http://semic2020.eu/	approx. 200	Moderation OpenData Track at SEMIC 2020
Profiles workshop	online workshop, collocated with the ISWC conference	LUH, UBO	ISWC conference	LUH, UBO	online	11.02.2020	ca. 40	academic	diss material	http://profiles2020.l3s.uni-hannover.de/	ca. 40	Organisation of the 7th International Workshop on Dataset PROFILING and Search
Symposium Intelligente Mobilität	symposium	LUH	LUH	LUH	Hannover, Germany	20/02/2020		80 all	poster presentation	http://sim2020.l3s.uni-hannover.de/	80	Poster presentation of the project during poster sessions at the symposium; networking with national projects and other event participants
Big Data and Security (BDS) Internal Innovation workshop	online conference	ATOS	ATOS	Internal Global Accounts of Atos for BDS division / Atos Research and Innovation(ARI)	Paris, Madrid	02.04.2021	20	Industry	technology roadmap for smashHit framework	Not available	20	ATOS Global BDS division aims to discover the latest technology developments from Atos Research and Innovation to align product management vision towards the challenges of data-driven industries. In this sense, Atos (ARI) showcase the latest achievements and SW developments made during the last 3 years. SmashHit was once of the reference projects presented in quite correlation with AGORA data marketplace solution
BDVA/DAIRO Activity Group meeting 43, 18th - 19th of March SESSION 2: Two-sided/Multi-sided aspects of data platforms	Workshop presentation	BDVA/DAIRO		ATB	online	18.03.2021	ca. 150	all	online presentation	not available	approx 150	
Colloquium on data science and artificial intelligence	colloquium	Wageningen University & Research		UIBK	online; Wageningen	several meetings late in 2020 and early in 2021	ca. 40	academic	presentation		ca. 40	Presentations of the project's developments in data sharing ecosystems (semantics, consent, automated contracting), for possible cooperations and uptake of the developments in other sectors, particularly, in agri-food (where WUR is the world-leading university).
GISRUK Online Seminar Series 2021	online conference			UBO, LUH	online	25/03/2021		30 all	keynote lecture	http://gisruk.org/seminar.html	30	Presentation of research results
2021 Oil and Gas High Performance Computing Conference	online conference	Rice University Ken Kennedy Institute	Rice University Ken Kennedy Institute	UIBK	online	03.05.2021		all	presentation	https://rice2021oghpc.rice.edu/ https://whova.com/portal/webapp/dsdw_202105/Agenda/1640430	ca. 30	Presented how semantic technology can be used to improve decision making with an use-case example of automatic contracting tool.
Data Week 2021 Workshop	online workshop	BDVA	EU, BDVA	ATB	online	26/05/2021	>30	all	presentation		ca. 30	Presentation in the session "Meta data interoperability"
BDVA Standards Workshop	Workshop	BDVA	EU, BDVA	TOG	online	07.06.2020	ca. 30	all	presentation	not available	ca. 30	SmashHit standardisation approach and areas of interests
Making Data Useful Conference	Conference	TOG	TOG	TOG	San Antonio, USA	28/01/2020	ca. 270	all	presentation	www.opengroup.org/sanantonio2020/proceedings/plenary	ca. 270	SmashHit project launch, objectives and expected impacts
H2020 Project Information Exchange	Project meeting	TOG, VW	TOG	TOG, VW, ATB	Athens, Greece	27/02/2020	ca. 28	all	presentation	not available	ca. 28	Technologies being used in VW BC in the SmashHit project
Open Digital Standards Conference	Online conference	TOG	TOG	TOG	online	27/01/2021	ca. 150	all	panel presentation	https://www.opengroup.org/open-digital-standards-0421/proceedings	ca. 150	SmashHit project progress update
Automotive Edge Hackathon	hackathon	Cariad/VW	Cariad	VW	online	19/10/2020-06/11/2020	ca. 50	Industry	coding and presentation	Not available		consent driven UBI enabler
Hackathon presentation	online conference	Cariad/VW	Cariad	VW	online	20/11/2020	ca. 50	Industry	presentation	Not available		consent driven UBI enabler
Internal meeting	meeting	Skoda	Skoda	VW	online	23/06/2021	ca. 10	Industry	presentation	Not available		consent driven UBI enabler
Internal meeting	meeting	Skoda	Skoda	VW	online	25/06/2021	ca. 10	Industry	presentation	Not available		consent driven UBI enabler
Internal meeting	meeting	Cariad	Cariad	VW	online	02.01.2021	ca. 10	Industry	presentation	Not available		consent driven UBI enabler
Internal meeting	meeting	Cariad	Cariad	VW	online	12.11.2020	ca. 10	Industry	presentation	Not available		consent driven UBI enabler
Internal meeting	meeting	Cariad	Cariad	VW	online	26/1/21	ca. 10	Industry	presentation	Not available		consent driven UBI enabler

